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Research Article

A New Stability Indicating Reverse Phase HPLC Method for the Simultaneous Determination of TPPO and TPP in the Presence of Phenylhydrazine Derivative in Penicillamine Drug Substance

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ABSTRACT

A simple, sensitive, selective, and reproducible stability indicating reverse phase HPLC method has been developed and validated for the determination of triphenylphosphine, triphenylphosphine oxide and phenylhydrazine derivative in penicillamine drug substance. Separation of analytes was carried out on an Ascentis Express C8 column. Column eluent consists of gradient mixing of ammonium dihydrogen orthophosphate as mobile phase A and acetonitrile as mobile phase B. Gradient elution at a flow rate of 0.8 mL/min, and injection volume is 10 μ L. The UV/Vis detector is set to a wavelength of 210 nm and the column oven is set at 20°C. The detector response was found to be linear over the concentration range of about 0.050 - 1.50 μ g/mL with correlation coefficients greater than 0.999 for triphenylphosphine oxide, phenylhydrazine derivative and triphenylphosphine. LOD value for these impurities is about 0.001 % w/w and LOQ values range from 0.002 to 0.003% w/w. The accuracy of the above analytes obtained by the proposed method was found to be in the range of 92- 104.6%. Degraded and process impurities are well separated and the method has been validated for specificity, precision, ruggedness, linearity, accuracy, and robustness as per ICH guidelines.

INTRODUCTION

Penicillamine is a conventional disease-modifying antirheumatic drug (DMARD) and is chemically identified as (2S)-2-Amino-3-methyl-3-

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sulfanylbutanoic acid (or) D-3-Mercaptovaline. The molecular formula is C₅H₁₁NO₂S and the molecular weight is 149.21. The chemical structure of Penicillamine is shown in Figure 1. Penicillamine is a heavy metal chelator, used in the treatment of Wilson disease, rheumatoid arthritis, and cystinuria. Penicillamine is a good chelating agent and highly soluble in water, it is generally resistant to metabolic degradation. It has a molecular structure adapted to binding metals, and retains this chelating activity despite the pH of body fluids. Penicillamine forms complexes with heavy metals that are less toxic than the free metallic ion. Penicillamine chelates copper through stable complex formation by thiol groups and this allows increased renal copper excretion [1].

Figure 1 Chemical Structure of Penicillamine Drug Substance.

Impurities present in drug substances and drug products can impact the quality, safety and efficacy of the drug substance and drug product. Triphenylphosphine (TPP), triphenyl phosphine oxide (TPPO) and phenylhydrazine derivative are the potential impurities existing in the route of synthesis of Penicillamine. Triphenylphosphine is a crucial and commonly used chemical that acts as a reducing agent in organometallic synthesis. Triphenylphosphine and triphenylphosphine oxide decompose on heating and produce toxic fumes, phosphorus oxides and phosphine (phosphorus trihydride). Exposure to triphenylphosphine and triphenylphosphine oxide cause skin and serious eye irritation, and may cause respiratory

irritation. Triphenylphosphine has low to moderate acute toxicity based on results from animal tests following acute oral exposure. In rats, the median lethal dose (LD₅₀) by the oral route ranged from approximately 700 mg/kg bw (in olive oil) to > 6400 mg/kg bw (in aqueous suspension), depending on the vehicle used. In mice, the oral LD₅₀ (in olive oil) was 1000 mg/kgbw. Toxic effects observed within 1-4 days of exposure included dyspnoea, apathy and impaired balance. The LD₅₀ was reported to be approximately 700 mg/kg bw [2]. Esa et al. evaluated triphenylphosphine and triphenylphosphine oxide have been shown to suppress immune responses in vitro [3]. In marine, exposure of triphenylphosphine oxide activated natural immune genes and disrupted lipid metabolism in mussels. Short-term exposure did not cause oxidative stress in mussels. Chronic exposure results in significant oxidative damage and oxidative stress in mussels [4]. A lethal dose of triphenylphosphine oxide for animals (beagle dogs) is a single oral dose, either 300 or 500mg/kg in corn oil leads fatal to uncoordinated body movements [5].

In the literature, various techniques have been reported for the quantification of triphenylphosphine (TPP) and triphenyl phosphine oxide [6-13] as triphenylphosphine oxide. A method for the determination of triphenylphosphine based on its oxidation to triphenylphosphine oxide by iodine or chloramine-T in acid medium in the presence of benzene or carbon tetrachloride is described [6]. Spectrophotometric determination of triphenylphosphine by molybdate 510 nm as phosphorus [7]. An isocratic reversed phase high performance liquid chromatographic method is described for monitoring concentrations of triphenylphosphine (TPP) and other compounds involved in an oxygen-transfer reaction catalyzed

by a molybdenum complex [8]. Determination of triphenylphosphine oxide (TPPO) in active pharmaceutical ingredients by HPLC [9]. A simple assay for lipid hydroperoxides based on triphenylphosphine oxidation and HPLC [10]. Determination of triphenylphosphine oxide for quantification of hydroperoxides in lipids by HPLC [11]. Determination of peroxide value of edible oils by FTIR spectroscopy using polyethylene film [12]. Measurement of peroxide values in oils by triphenylphosphine/triphenylphosphine oxide assay coupled with FTIR-ATR spectroscopy comparison with iodometric titration [13]. In above procedures triphenylphosphine is converted into triphenylphosphine oxide and triphenylphosphine oxide will be quantified.

So, it is important to develop a sensitive analytical method for the quantification of triphenylphosphine and triphenylphosphine oxide in drug substances. The interest of the study is to quantify both triphenylphosphine and triphenylphosphine oxide in a single method. Triphenylphosphine is slowly converted into triphenylphosphine oxide in aqueous solutions and it is stable in organic solvents like Acetonitrile and Methanol. In this study, a stability indicating reverse phase HPLC method for the determination of triphenylphosphine, triphenylphosphine oxide and phenylhydrazine derivative impurities in Penicillamine drug substance has been developed, optimized and validated as per the ICH guidelines [14].

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Materials:

Penicillamine and its related substances were prepared in APL Research Centre-II (A Division of Aurobindo Pharma Ltd). Triphenylphosphine and triphenylphosphine oxide standards purchased

from Sigma Aldrich. Ammonium dihydrogen phosphate, HPLC grade acetonitrile, HPLC grade methanol, hydrochloric acid, sodium hydroxide and hydrogen peroxide were purchased from Merck India. Milli-Q grade (Millipore, MA, USA) water was used during experiments. 0.45µm PVDF membrane filters were procured from Merck Life Science Pvt Ltd.

Instrumentation:

All experiments were carried out on a Waters alliance e2695 (Waters Corporation, Milford, MA, USA), separation module consisting of a binary pump, column oven, and an auto-injector equipped with 2489 UV/Visible detector. Peak purity was performed on 2998 photodiode array detector (PDA). Empower software was used for signal monitoring and data processing.

Preparation of standard, sample and Buffer solutions:

The standard solution was prepared at a level of about 1 µg/mL each of Triphenylphosphine oxide, Phenylhydrazine derivative and Triphenylphosphine reference standards in diluent by diluting stock solution containing 0.25 mg/ml. Methanol is used as a diluent. A sample solution at about 2 mg/ml concentration is prepared diluent.

Buffer solution of 0.01M ammonium dihydrogen phosphate was prepared by dissolving 1.15 g/L of the respective salt in water. Buffer solution was filtered through 0.45 µm porosity membrane filter. Buffer solution is used as Mobile phase A. Acetonitrile is used as Mobile phase B.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Method development:

The aim of the work is simultaneous determination of triphenylphosphine oxide, triphenylphosphine

and phenylhydrazine derivative. The proposed analytical method should separate other related substances from analytes. Method development initiated by using a HPLC column consists of octadecylsilane (C18) as a stationary phase. Phosphoric acid and acetonitrile are used as mobile phase A and B with a gradient elution ($T_{\min} / \% B$ - 0/50, 28/80, 33/80, 35/50, 45/50) at a flow rate of 1.0ml/min. In this phase columns Triphenylphosphine oxide and TPP are well separated. The triphenylphosphine oxide and phenylhydrazine derivatives have very less resolution in the octadecylsilane stationary phase. Octylsilane (C8) stationary phase used to separate the analytes. In this experiment, triphenylphosphine oxide and phenylhydrazine derivatives have less resolution. A column having sub-3-micron particle size with core technology is used to improve the resolution between triphenylphosphine oxide and phenylhydrazine derivatives and reduce the back pressure. Mobile phase A is changed to ammonium dihydrogen orthophosphate at a concentration of 0.01M is used to improve the resolution. Chromatographic parameters are optimized to get optimal resolution between triphenylphosphine oxide and phenylhydrazine derivatives and avoid

interferences from sample matrices. The resolution between triphenylphosphine oxide and phenylhydrazine derivative is set as system suitability criteria for the proposed analytical method and the proposed method has been validated as per the ICH guidelines.

Detection Method:

Separation of analytes is achieved on an Ascentis Express C8 column with dimensions of 150mm x 4.6 mm and 2.7 μm . Analytes are eluted through gradient elution by using 0.01M ammonium dihydrogen phosphate buffer and Acetonitrile are used as Mobile phase A and Mobile phase B respectively. The proposed gradient programme for the separation is ($T_{\min} / \% \text{ of Mobile phase-B}$) 0/40, 10/70, 25/70, 27/40, 35/40 at a flow rate of 0.8ml/min. The analytical column was thermostated at a temperature of 20°C and the analytes were monitored at 210 nm by injecting 10 μL of sample solution. The retention times of triphenylphosphine oxide, phenylhydrazine derivative and Triphenylphosphine are about 5.6, 6.0 and 17minutes respectively and molecular structures are shown in figure 2.

Figure 2 Chemical Structures of analytes.

METHOD VALIDATIONS

The proposed method has been validated as per ICH guidelines to prove its competence. The validation parameters studied were specificity, sensitivity, linearity, precision (Repeatability and Intermediate precision), accuracy, and robustness.

The results obtained from the experiments are summarized in the next paragraphs.

System suitability:

The standard solution at a level of about 1 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ each of Triphenylphosphine oxide, Phenylhydrazine derivative and

Triphenylphosphine is injected into the HPLC system for system suitability. The resolution between “Triphenylphosphine oxide and Phenylhydrazine derivative” peaks is a minimum of 2. The column efficiency is determined from the

phenylhydrazine derivative peak is not less than 12000 USP plate counts and USP tailing for the same peak is not more than 1.5. Representative chromatogram of standard solution is shown in figure 3.

Figure 3 Representative HPLC chromatogram of Standard – Triphenylphosphine oxide, Phenylhydrazine derivative and Triphenylphosphine.

The RSD for the respective peak areas of six injections of the standard solution is not more than 5.0%. The results are tabulated in Table 1.

Table 1 System suitability			
Injection ID	Peak area of		
	Triphenyl phosphine oxide	Phenylhydrazine derivative	Triphenylphosphine
1	82774	62944	93977
2	80022	61040	91621
3	83911	63539	96051
4	83911	63561	96652
5	83730	63818	97016
6	84127	63491	97023
Mean	83079	63066	95390
SD	1571	1033	2170
% RSD	1.9	1.6	2.3
95% Confidence interval (\pm)	1649	1084	2278

Specificity:

Specificity stands for the ability of the method to judge the analytes accurately in the presence of other components present in the sample matrix. The specificity and stability indicating nature of the proposed method is performed in the presence of forced degradation. The wet and dried forced

degradation studies of penicillamine were subjected to acid, base, peroxide, thermal, photolytic, and humidity conditions. Stress studies were performed at a test concentration level for the penicillamine drug substance. Conditions were tabulated in Table 2. Stressed samples were analyzed using the PDA detector to evaluate the ability of the proposed method to separate the

degradation products from analytes. formed during all the stress conditions. This Triphenylphosphine oxide, phenylhydrazine implies that the proposed method was specific. derivative and triphenylphosphine were not

Table 2 Specificity	
Degradation	Degradation condition
-	Undegraded sample
Acid	2.5M HCl/85°C/120 minutes
Base	2.5M NaoH/85°C/120 minutes
Peroxide	0.25% H2O2/RT/Initial
Thermal	105°C/120 hours
Photolytic	White fluorescent light, 1.2 million Lux hours and UV light, 200 watt hours / meter ²
Humidity	92.5% RH/25°C /120 hours

Representative chromatograms of Triphenyl phosphine oxide, Phenylhydrazine derivative and Triphenyl phosphine is shown in figure 4 - 6.

Figure 4 Representative HPLC chromatograms of Triphenylphosphine oxide.

Figure 5 Representative HPLC chromatograms of Phenylhydrazine derivative.

Figure 6 Representative HPLC chromatograms of Triphenylphosphine.

Limit of Detection and Limit of Quantification:

Limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantification (LOQ) are the key parameters which reveal the sensitivity of an analytical method. The LOD and LOQ concentrations were estimated for triphenylphosphine oxide, phenylhydrazine derivative and triphenylphosphine by using the slope of the linearity curve, ranging from 5 to 150% of the specification level. Predicted concentrations of

LOD and LOQ solutions for analytes were prepared and injected into HPLC as per the methodology. The % RSD values for the precision of analytes ranged from 0.9 – 2.3 and 0.4 – 3.5 for LOD and LOQ, respectively. From these results, it was concluded that the proposed method had adequate sensitivity for the detection and quantification of triphenylphosphine oxide, phenylhydrazine derivative and triphenylphosphine in Penicillamine drug substance. The results are tabulated in Table 3.

Injection ID	Area					
	Triphenylphosphine oxide		Phenylhydrazine derivative		Triphenylphosphine	
	LOD	LOQ	LOD	LOQ	LOD	LOQ
1	1506	4460	1100	3308	3310	936
2	1500	4441	1143	3317	3276	943
3	1477	4429	1176	3342	3339	884
4	1492	4481	1149	3343	3443	899
5	1476	4428	1125	3355	3395	926
6	1471	4440	1123	3349	3453	975
Mean	1487	4447	1136	3336	3369	927
SD	14	20	26	19	72	32
% RSD	0.9	0.4	2.3	0.6	2.1	3.5
Conc. ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	0.016	0.049	0.016	0.049	0.05	0.017
Conc. (% w/w)	0.001	0.002	0.001	0.002	0.003	0.001

Linearity:

The linearity of an analytical method will determine the range of that proposed method, in which the results are directly proportional to the concentration of the analyte in the sample. Linearity was performed by injecting ten diluted solutions ranging from LOQ to 150% of the specification level. The linearity was evaluated by

linear regression analysis, i.e., $y = mx + c$, where y is the peak area, x is the concentration, and m and c values represented the slope and intercept, respectively. The correlation coefficients for triphenylphosphine oxide, phenylhydrazine derivative and triphenylphosphine from the linear graph were found to be 0.9999, 0.9999 and 0.9990 respectively. The results are tabulated in Table 4.

Name of the impurity	Statistical analysis		
	Triphenylphosphine oxide	Phenylhydrazine derivative	Triphenylphosphine
Conc. Range ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	0.049 - 1.484	0.049 - 1.483	0.050 - 1.512
Slope	85084	65968	90799
Intercept	480	362	-5179
Residual sum of squares	2025685	1270731	40914724
Correlation coefficient	0.9999	0.9999	0.999

Accuracy:

Accuracy was demonstrated by the standard addition method, in which known quantities of triphenylphosphine oxide, phenylhydrazine derivative and triphenylphosphine were added to the penicillamine sample solution. Spiked solutions were prepared in triplicate at the LOQ

level and 50 – 150 % w/w level. The analytes of penicillamine were determined from the spiked sample solutions and the percent recovery was calculated, and it was found to lie in between 95.1 and 103.7 %w/w. The statistical analysis showed that the method was accurate. The results are tabulated in Table 5.

Table 5 Accuracy at LOQ, 50, 100 and 150% levels				
Accuracy parameter	LOQ level	50 % level	100 % level	150% level
Triphenylphosphine oxide				
Amount added (% w/w)	0.0025	0.0246	0.0491	0.0736
Amount found (% w/w)	0.0025	0.0257	0.0507	0.0759
% Recovery	100.0	104.6	103.5	103.0
% RSD	0.0	0.2	0.2	0.3
Overall % Recovery	102.8			
Phenylhydrazine derivative				
Amount added (% w/w)	0.0025	0.0245	0.0489	0.0734
Amount found (% w/w)	0.0025	0.0233	0.0478	0.0677
% Recovery	100.0	95.2	97.7	92.2
% RSD	0.0	0.2	0.5	0.1
Overall % Recovery	96.3			
Triphenylphosphine				
Amount added (% w/w)	0.0025	0.0249	0.0498	0.0734
Amount found (% w/w)	0.0023	0.0251	0.0510	0.0677
% Recovery	92.0	100.7	102.5	92.2
% RSD	0.0	0.6	0.2	0.1
Overall % Recovery	96.9			

Representative chromatograms of spiked sample, sample and diluents are shown in figure 4 - 6.

Figure 7 Representative HPLC chromatograms of Penicillamine drug substance - Spiked with Triphenylphosphine oxide, Phenylhydrazine derivative and Triphenylphosphine.

Figure 8 Representative HPLC chromatograms of Penicillamine drug substance –As such sample.

Figure 9 Representative HPLC chromatograms of Diluent

Precision:

The system precision has been demonstrated by injecting six replicate injections of standard solution into the HPLC system and the %RSD of area response for six replicate measurements was found to be less than 5.

Method precision has been evaluated by means of repeatability and intermediate precision. To determine the repeatability and intermediate precision of the method, replicated (n=6) injections of the spiked sample at specification level of analytes of penicillamine were carried out and precision was expressed as % RSD. The results are tabulated in Table 6.

Table 6 Method Precision (MP) and Intermediate Precision (IP)

Sample ID	Triphenylphosphine oxide		Phenylhydrazine derivative		Triphenylphosphine	
	MP	IP	MP	IP	MP	IP
Sample-1	0.0507	0.0505	0.0481	0.0464	0.0510	0.0492
Sample-2	0.0506	0.0500	0.0477	0.0457	0.0510	0.0487
Sample-3	0.0508	0.0501	0.0476	0.0454	0.0511	0.0481
Sample-4	0.0504	0.0505	0.0472	0.0457	0.0508	0.0485
Sample-5	0.0507	0.0498	0.0471	0.045	0.0510	0.0482
Sample-6	0.0511	0.0500	0.0474	0.0448	0.0514	0.0478
Mean	0.0507	0.0502	0.0475	0.0455	0.0511	0.0484
S.D.	0.0002	0.0003	0.0004	0.0006	0.0002	0.0005
% RSD	0.4	0.6	0.8	1.3	0.4	1.0
95% Confidence interval (±)	0.0002	0.0003	0.0004	0.0006	0.0002	0.0005
Overall Statistical data:						
Mean	0.0504		0.0465		0.0497	

S.D.	0.0004	0.0011	0.0014
% RSD	0.8	2.4	2.8
95% Confidence interval (\pm)	0.0003	0.0007	0.009

Robustness:

Robustness of the method indicates the ability of the method to remain unchanged even after variations in critical method parameters. The effect of variation in flow, percentage organic gradient composition, column oven temperature,

and detection wavelength on system suitability criteria was studied. The resolutions between triphenylphosphine oxide and phenylhydrazine derivative were found to be more than 3.0 in each variation, which indicates the robustness of the method. The statistical analysis of robustness data was illustrated in Table 7.

Condition	Variation	USP plate count	USP Tailing	USP resolution*
Existing	-	24225	1.0	3.9
Flow rate	-10%	26538	1.0	3.9
	10%	20538	1.0	3.7
% of Organic in gradient composition	-2% absolute	55451	1.0	5.4
	+2% absolute	39577	1.1	4.7
Column oven Temperature	-5°C	55818	1.2	5.8
	+5°C	55155	1.2	5.8
Wavelength	-3 nm	19555	1.0	4.1
	+3 nm	21630	1.0	3.0

*USP resolution between Triphenylphosphine oxide and Phenylhydrazine derivative

Solution stability:

Stability of the penicillamine spiked sample solution at test concentration and standard solution were studied by keeping the solutions at room temperature and $5^{\circ}\text{C}\pm 3^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 24 h. The standard solution was stable for at least 24 h at $5^{\circ}\text{C}\pm 3^{\circ}\text{C}$ and the sample solution was stable for at least 14 h at $5^{\circ}\text{C}\pm 3^{\circ}\text{C}$ for refrigerator condition.

CONCLUSION

This optimized method to determine the triphenylphosphine oxide, phenylhydrazine derivative and triphenylphosphine in Penicillamine is simple, efficient, rapid, selective, and sensitive. “The low cost per analysis, shorter analysis time and simultaneous determination of triphenylphosphine oxide and triphenylphosphine

in presence of phenylhydrazine derivative” are noted to be specific advantages of this method is over the other methods reported so far. This method was validated as per ICH guidelines and the results obtained from validation experiments proved that this optimized method is selective, sensitive, linear, precise, accurate, robust and rugged. Therefore, this optimized method is suitable for the intended purpose and can be used during routine.

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